

Relationship between Stiffness of Texture Material and Perceived Roughness: A Numerical Analysis

Toru Hamasaki^[0000-0002-0652-5508] and Masami Iwamoto^[0000-0002-0738-521X]

Toyota Central R&D Labs., Inc., Nagakute, Japan
hamasaki@mosk.tytlabs.co.jp

Abstract. Investigating the relationship between the stiffness of a texture material and perceived roughness could potentially enhance the tactile comfort of industrial products. This study aimed to investigate this relationship when a dot-textured surface was scanned across the finger pad, by a numerical simulation model comprising mechanical, neurophysiological, and perceived roughness models. We tested materials with Young's modulus (E) of 0.05, 0.15, 0.5, 2, 10, and 100 MPa at the surface. The simulation indicated a significant change in perceived roughness at a texture stiffness of $E = 2$ MPa equivalent to that of the stratum corneum. This study contributes to a better understanding of this relationship and the application of such a numerical model to digital engineering tools for the development of industrial products in digital transformation.

Keywords: Computational model, Perceived roughness, Material stiffness.

1 Introduction

Research on the relationship between the texture material stiffness and perceived roughness could potentially enhance the tactile comfort of industrial products [1]. Utilizing numerical simulation models facilitates quantitative evaluation of touch feeling and can accelerate the development of industrial products while reducing costs. This study aimed to investigate the relationship between texture stiffness and perceived roughness when a dot-textured surface was scanned across the finger pad, by a numerical simulation model [2,3]. We hypothesized significant changes in this relationship when the stiffness of a texture material was below that of the stratum corneum (SC). The SC is the outermost layer of the skin and has the highest stiffness of the other underlying tissues, which protects the other tissues from harm.

2 Methods

The numerical simulation model in this study consisted of three parts [2–5]: (1) mechanical model using finite element method which reproduced finger skin deformation upon contact with an object (Fig. 1), (2) neurophysiological model, inspired by the model of Gerling et al. [4], which simulated neural responses of mechanoreceptors (slowly adapting type 1 (SA1) afferents) induced by the skin deformation, and (3)

perceived roughness model proposed by Connor et al. [5] that estimated the perception from the spatial variation of SA1 neural responses.

A comparison between the present model and experimental data [6] was conducted to validate the model for estimating perceived roughness when dot-textured surfaces were scanned. The results demonstrate the reliability of the model (Fig. 2).

For the present investigation, a simple ellipsoid dot structure (Fig. 1) was employed to simplify creation of textures in future psychophysical experiments. A scanning speed of 20 mm/s and contact force of 0.6 N were set as the simulation condition [6]. Young's modulus (E) values of 0.05, 0.15, 0.5, 2, 10, and 100 MPa were adopted for material properties of the textured surface. The modulus of elasticity of SC was approximately 2 MPa during the simulation, while it was represented by a non-linear material model [2]. The mechanical simulation was executed using the commercial finite element software Abaqus (SIMULIA, Dassault Systemes, France).

Fig. 1. Mechanical model for this investigation.

Fig. 2. Validation of present model.

3 Results and Discussion

Within the conditions of the texture stiffness ranging from 2 MPa to 100 MPa, which is stiffer than the stiffness of SC, variations in the texture stiffness had minimal effect on the amount of the texture and skin deformation (the three on the right in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b)). Consequently, the influence of variations in the texture stiffness on SA1 firing was also slight (Fig. 3(c)), resulting in a limited influence of these variations on perceived roughness (Fig. 3(d)). In contrast, when the texture stiffness was below 2 MPa, which is lower than that of the SC, the skin deformation reduced since the texture itself deformed upon contact with the skin (the three on the left in Figs. 3(a) and 3(b)). The subsequent neural responses also decreased (Fig. 3(c)), resulting in lower perception of roughness (Fig. 3(d)).

Condo et al. [7] reported that SA1 responses were weaker when the finger contacted with softer materials as opposed to harder ones. Sakaguchi et al. [8] suggested that the stiffness of SC affects tactile sensitivity. The variation in perceived roughness between 0.05MPa to 2MPa complied with Fechner's law ($R^2 = 0.98$) and Stevens's law ($R^2 = 0.93$). We believe that the numerical simulation model yielded reasonable results. As future works, we need to validate these results with data from psychophysiological experiments that includes the investigation of comfortability related to texture stiffness. In addition, further studies should consider rapidly adapting and Pacinian afferents and skin behavior associated with friction.

Fig. 3. (a) Texture and skin deformation (Fig. 1). Textures are displayed in contour plots about compressive displacement. (b) Skin deformation (strain energy density) at the border between epidermis and dermis. (c) SA1 firing responses during scanning. (d) Estimation of perceived roughness against changes of texture stiffness.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors declare no conflicts of interest associated with this article.

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